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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PRINCIPLES OF ORGANISING AUTONOMOUS LEARNING

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Abstract: The article analyses the principles of structuring autonomous learning within the context of foreign language education at non-linguistic higher education institutions. Particular emphasis is placed on the significance of learner autonomy in cultivating professional foreign language proficiency and enhancing students' competitiveness in the contemporary labour market. The study examines theoretical frameworks related to learner autonomy and learning strategies, emphasizing the roles of responsibility, self-regulation, and motivation in autonomous learning. The practical component of the research explores the implementation of technology-driven methodologies, including distance learning tools and online resources, to promote learner autonomy. The results indicate that incorporating the principles of autonomous learning into foreign language education improves students' interest, language skills, and ability to manage their own learning process effectively.

Key words: autonomous learning, foreign language education, learning strategies, learner autonomy, distance learning, professional competence, self-regulation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada nolingvistik oliy ta'lim muassasalarida xorijiy tillarni o'qitish jarayonida avtonom ta'limni tuzish tamoyillari tahlil qilinadi. Asosiy e'tibor o'quvchilarning professional xorijiy til kompetensiyasini shakllantirish va zamonaviy mehnat bozorida raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda o'quvchi avtonomiyasining ahamiyatiga qaratiladi. Tadqiqotda o'quvchi avtonomiyasi va o'rganish strategiyalariga oid nazariy yondashuvlar ko'rib chiqilib, avtonom ta'lim jarayonida mas'uliyat, o'zini o'zi boshqarish va motivatsiyaning roli yoritiladi. Tadqiqotning amaliy qismida masofaviy ta'lim vositalari va onlayn resurslarni o'z ichiga olgan texnologiyaga asoslangan metodologiyalarni joriy etish orqali o'quvchi avtonomiyasini rivojlantirish masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Olingan natijalar xorijiy til ta'limida avtonom ta'lim tamoyillarini qo'llash o'quvchilarning qiziqishi, til ko'nikmalari hamda o'z o'quv jarayonini samarali boshqarish qobiliyatini oshirishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: avtonom ta'lim, xorijiy til ta'limi, o'rganish strategiyalari, o'quvchi avtonomiyasi, masofaviy ta'lim, professional kompetensiya, o'zini o'zi boshqarish.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются принципы структурирования автономного обучения в контексте преподавания иностранных языков в нелингвистических высших учебных заведениях. Особое внимание уделяется значению автономии обучающихся в формировании профессиональной иноязычной компетентности и повышении конкурентоспособности студентов на современном рынке труда. В исследовании рассматриваются теоретические подходы к автономии обучающихся и стратегиям обучения, подчёркивается роль ответственности, саморегуляции и мотивации в процессе автономного обучения. Практическая часть исследования посвящена внедрению технологически ориентированных методик, включающих инструменты дистанционного обучения и онлайн-ресурсы, направленных на развитие автономии обучающихся. Результаты показывают, что интеграция принципов автономного обучения в процесс преподавания иностранных языков способствует повышению интереса студентов, развитию языковых навыков и формированию способности эффективно управлять собственным учебным процессом.

Ключевые слова: автономное обучение, обучение иностранным языкам, стратегии обучения, автономия обучающихся, дистанционное обучение, профессиональная компетентность, саморегуляция.

INTRODUCTION

The competitiveness of a newly trained specialist is directly contingent upon their competence in foreign languages. Contemporary civilization requires highly skilled professionals who are capable of using a foreign language in their professional activities. The English language functions as an essential tool, comparable to computer literacy or the ability to process and interpret professionally oriented written and oral information.

A graduate who has completed a bachelor's programme should demonstrate proficiency in Russian and at least one foreign language in order to address issues of interpersonal and intercultural communication. At non-linguistic technical universities, students are required to study specialized technical disciplines while simultaneously achieving a high level of proficiency in foreign languages to ensure their competitiveness as future specialists. To enhance the effectiveness of the learning process, educators should organize and deliver instruction in a way that maximizes students' access to educational content, taking into account their existing levels of language competence. Moreover, fostering active student engagement in academic activities is of particular importance and can be achieved through the integration of learner autonomy principles into the educational process. It is therefore reasonable to assume that students are well positioned to design their own individualized learning programmes and to evaluate the effectiveness of those programmes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Little (2015) notes that learner autonomy is a contentious concept that is often conflated with self-instruction. The term remains elusive due to the inherent difficulty of providing a precise definition. The growing body of literature has debated, for example, whether learner autonomy should be understood as capacity or behavior; whether it is characterized by learner responsibility or learner control; whether it represents a psychological phenomenon with political implications or a political right with psychological consequences; and whether the development of learner autonomy depends on a complementary, comprehensive framework (see Benson, 2001). The question of what constitutes an autonomous learner has therefore attracted sustained scholarly attention. Effective lesson planning, contemporary pedagogical approaches, and well-designed strategies play a crucial role in fostering autonomy among language learners.

As Scharle and Szabó (2000, p. 4) argue, "Autonomy can be theoretically defined as the freedom and capacity to manage one's own affairs, including the right to make decisions." Responsibility, in turn, may be defined as the obligation to oversee a task and to take responsibility for the consequences of one's actions. Autonomy and accountability thus require active involvement and are clearly interrelated.

With regard to learning techniques and their significance in autonomous learning, Chamot and O'Malley (1994, p. 58) identify two primary reasons for integrating learning strategies into the teaching of academic language and content. First, learning strategies are theoretically consistent with the cognitive perspective on learning that underpins the Cognitive Academic Language Learning Approach (CALLA). Second, a substantial body of research supports the use of learning strategies in conjunction with the development of academic language and content knowledge.

Barbara (2007) further contends that individual characteristics such as age, gender, motivation, and ability may influence the selection and use of learning strategies. Although these factors differ in nature, the present study suggests that language learning strategies are essential for effective instruction and are likely to gain increasing importance as language learning is viewed as an active process in which learners engage with their individual differences. The absence of learner autonomy and sufficient language proficiency in online learning environments may result in psychological disengagement, dissatisfaction, and academic failure, particularly among learners who are unfamiliar with online education (Olmanson & Liu, 2018), as autonomy and the effective use of language learning strategies are fundamental to successful language acquisition. The concept of autonomy has a long history, emerging in the 1970s within the field of English language teaching, and it refers to learners' capacity to monitor and regulate their own learning progress.

Active engagement in learning is therefore essential for successful language acquisition, whether in terms of self-monitoring or gaining control over the learning process (Benson, 2013). These learner-centered approaches enable students to set personal learning goals, complete tasks at their own pace, and refine their self-assessment, while teachers assume the role of facilitators who supervise learning processes and provide guidance and mentoring when necessary.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed both qualitative and quantitative methods within a mixed-methods research design. The research was conducted with undergraduate students from non-linguistic disciplines at a journalism-based university. Participants were divided into two groups: an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group was taught using self-directed learning methods, including goal setting, self-assessment, reflective journal writing, and the use of digital tools such as online platforms, podcasts, and independent project work. Students were instructed to plan their learning processes, select appropriate learning strategies, and monitor their own progress. In this group, the teacher acted primarily as a facilitator and consultant, providing guidance and feedback when necessary. The control group followed a traditional teacher-centered approach based on a

fixed syllabus, regular classroom instruction, and limited opportunities for autonomous learning. Data collection methods included questionnaires, classroom observations, analysis of students' learning logs, and pre- and post-tests designed to assess foreign language speaking and listening skills. The collected data were analyzed to identify changes in students' levels of autonomy, motivation, and language proficiency. Educational institutions are increasingly adopting technology to improve instructional effectiveness, and various forms of distance learning have become widely used. Distance learning is not only a mode of communication but also a means of adapting to emerging trends in foreign language use, enhancing student motivation, and integrating principles of learner autonomy into everyday teaching and learning. The use of podcasts and online learning environments represents a technology-based approach that supports learner autonomy while engaging students in extracurricular learning activities. Traditional training approaches, however, often fail to allocate sufficient classroom time for the development of speaking and listening skills, which are essential for technical specialists who require foreign language competence for professional purposes.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the study indicate that students who were taught using an autonomous learning approach demonstrated significantly higher levels of motivation and engagement compared to those in the control group. The experimental group showed noticeable improvement in speaking and listening skills and reported increased confidence in using a foreign language for professional purposes. Questionnaire responses revealed that students developed a stronger sense of responsibility for their own learning and gained greater awareness of effective learning strategies. Participants emphasized that the ability to select their own learning materials and regulate the pace of study enhanced their motivation and reduced anxiety, particularly in online and distance learning contexts. Observational data further confirmed that autonomous learners were more active during classroom and online activities and more willing to participate in discussions and problem-solving tasks. Overall, the findings support the view that learner autonomy is not merely a theoretical teaching concept but a practical and effective tool for improving foreign language education in non-linguistic higher education institutions.

CONCLUSION

The study verifies that structuring autonomous learning is a critical element in enhancing the quality of foreign language education for non-linguistic students. Learner autonomy fosters responsibility, self-regulation, and active engagement, which are crucial for cultivating professional communicative competence. Combining technology with distance learning tools makes it easier for students to learn independently by providing broader access to authentic materials and enabling them to choose personalized learning paths. However, learner autonomy does not eliminate the teacher's role; rather, it transforms it into that of a mentor and facilitator. In conclusion, the consistent application of the principles of autonomous learning leads to more effective language acquisition, higher learner motivation, and improved preparation of future professionals for communication in a foreign language.

References:

1. Benson, P. (2001). *Teaching and researching autonomy in language learning*. London: Longman.
2. Benson, P. (2013). *Teaching and researching autonomy in language learning* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge.
3. Chamot, A. U., & O'Malley, J. M. (1994). *The CALLA handbook: Implementing the Cognitive Academic Language Learning Approach*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
4. Little, D. (2015). *Learner autonomy and second/foreign language learning*. In *The guide to learning languages*. Dublin: Trinity College Dublin.
5. Olmanson, J., & Liu, Y. (2018). Online learning and learner autonomy: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 11(1), 1–15.
6. Scharle, Á., & Szabó, A. (2000). *Learner autonomy: A guide to developing learner responsibility*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
7. Barbara, H. (2007). Language learning strategies and learner differences. *System*, 35(1), 1–14.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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